

Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray—His Message to the Nation*

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I greatly appreciate the unique honour bestowed upon me by the Indian Chemical Society in inviting me to deliver this year's Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray Memorial Lecture. This invitation has given me an opportunity to pay my sincere tribute to revered Acharya Prafulla Chandraji who was always regarded by my Guru, Dr. Shanti Swarup Bhatnagar, as his Grand-Guru.

Acharya Ray was one of those glorious sons of Bharatavarsha who practised and preached truths realised by him through hard work. He was enthused with the spirit of service and sacrifice; he worked untiringly and zealously not for self-elevation, but towards the banishment of the grinding poverty and abysmal ignorance prevailing in his Motherland and raising her in the esteem of the world at large. With a view to making his countrymen face the problems of life squarely, he tried to inculcate in them the ideal of the dignity of labour and to create in young men an abiding interest in the pursuit of science. With these ends in view he formulated some definite and effective plans and, being fully conscious of the tremendous hardships these involve, he set an example himself before he asked others to act on them.

The purpose of the Indian Chemical Society in organising memorial lectures in the name of Acharyaji is therefore not merely to honour the memory of this sage of our age, but also to perpetuate the manifold services he rendered towards the economic and scientific advancement of our country, to make our people strong, progressive, and prosperous.

I neither had the privilege of working with Professor Ray in his laboratories nor did I get any opportunity of intimate association with him in any of his numerous activities. I am therefore not in a position to speak on the instructive and revealing subject of Acharya Ray's reminiscences which were selected by some of his pupils on this occasion to pen the memories of their association with their illustrious Guru. I feel that it will be superfluous to give an account of the immense amount of chemical work done by Acharyaji, because firstly, every serious student of chemistry is quite familiar with it and secondly, fairly exhaustive articles have already been published on the subject by Dr. J. N. Ray and the present speaker. Therefore, I thought it would be very appropriate to recapitulate at this momentous period in the history of our country the ideals which Acharyaji had placed before us with a view to inspiring our young men as well as elders to work hard for their own benefit and for the good of the country. Hence I have chosen to speak this evening on 'Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray-his Message to the

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Nation'. This deals with the salient, characteristic, and illuminating aspects of his life and work as a scholar, teacher, chemical investigator, educationist, writer, social reformer, pioneer in the advancement of science in India, philanthropist, and patriot. I have tried to present the information available on these topics in such a manner as to convince every listener or reader that Acharyaji led an ideal life in perfect consonance with the principles laid down by the greatest seers. The significance of Acharyaji's ways of life concerned with these aspects has been further emphasised by pointing out the present undesirable and unhappy situations arising from actions contrary to Acharyaji's methods, and by suggesting, wherever possible, remedies based on his practices.

My second lecture, which will deal with some aspects of gel-formation, will be delivered under the auspices of the Bombay Branch of the Indian Chemical Society.

ACHARYAJI—A GREAT SCHOLAR

According to Hindu scriptures, a scholar is a *Brahmachari*, who would be intelligent; pure in body, mind, and spirit; well-wisher of all living beings; good in behaviour; particularly careful in diet; complete master of his sense organs; celibate; and abstainer from the company of women and obscene sights. A scholar is thus characterised by not only his insatiable thirst for knowledge and devotion to duty but also for several other requisites. This means that scholarship is not only merely an accomplishment in learning but also an acquisition of a discipline which, when directed to studies, leads to erudition.

It will be clear from what follows that Prafulla Chandra was a scholar in the true sense. Throughout he lived the life of an ideal *Brahmacharin* and pursued incessantly the quest for knowledge, which he regarded as more precious than anything else in the world. From his childhood he developed a great liking for history, geography, and English and Bengali literatures and kept up his interest in these subjects till the last. He possessed an unusual faculty for deep and systematic study; this is revealed by his capacity for quoting long passages from the writings of several authors. His keenness for intensive study is also shown by his proficiency in languages; besides possessing a perfect command over English and Bengali, he had a good knowledge also of Sanskrit, French, German, and Latin which he learnt through self-effort.

Naturally the selection of the institutions for his education was made primarily on the distinction of their teachers who could quench his insatiable thirst for deeper and wider knowledge. Hence he joined Albert School for pre-entrance course and later Metropolitan Institution for post-entrance studies, although there was no provision for the teaching of physics and chemistry in this institution and for which he had to go to the Presidency College. It was at this college that he was inspired to study chemistry and the interest created impelled him not only to read most of the available books on the subject but also to establish a miniature laboratory of his own, a tendency often seen in eminent scientists.

Acharyaji pursued the study of chemistry up to the then highest standard in India and later in England where he could go by virtue of his meritorious performance at the Gilchrist scholarship competitive examination. He conducted research work in inorganic chemistry at the laboratories of the University of Edinburgh which was at that time recognised as the premier seat of learning in Great Britain. These investigations are described in his thesis entitled, 'Conjugate Sulphates of the Copper-magnesium Group—a

Study of Isomorphous Mixtures and Molecular Combinations', for which he was awarded the D. Sc. degree by the University. This was a rare distinction, as these awards were 'few and far between' in those days. This work was later published in the Proceedings of the Royal Society of Edinburgh.

Prafulla Chandra's attainments as a scholar were due not only to his inborn genius but also to his hard work, the personal care of his father, and the circumstances in which he was brought up. Shri Harish Chandra Ray, Acharyaji's father, was a great scholar and was proficient in English and Persian. He had a good collection of literary works.

To-day independent India stands in great and urgent need of scholars who can attain eminence in diverse subjects, but there are only a few persons with inborn faculties for learning and power of comprehension. Acharyaji's life teaches us that a good deal of the requirements can be met if the scholars sincerely work hard, the parents pay personal attention to them, an atmosphere of learning, facilities for education exist at home, and opportunities are provided for receiving education under the guidance of distinguished teachers.

The parents, though seemingly preoccupied with various affairs, should devote some reasonable time for free discussion with their children. Acharyaji tells us that he gained more knowledge from free conversations with his father on all conceivable topics than through books. I personally know the efficacy of this method of education which was practised by a school Headmaster for the training of his son who, in spite of his present high position in the administrative department of the Government, has retained his love for learning and study and finds time out of his multifarious heavy engagements for original writing.

Like Acharyaji's father, the parents should also help to develop the reading habit of their children by providing some really good and inspiring books at home. The saying, 'a home without books is a body without soul', also lays stress on this requirement. There are only a few genuine lovers of books who can indulge in this expensive habit. This deficiency should somehow be made up, at least by the parents of deserving scholars, at any cost; otherwise it could be compensated by arranging for a small but efficient reading room by private agencies in different localities of every town.

The educational authorities should plan to establish some institution where the gifted and the talented scholars can receive education from the inspired and devoted teachers who are widely read, have a deep insight and a clear grasp of a subject, and by their significant original contributions have attained eminence in the academic world, and who consider it their sacred duty to dedicate themselves to their pupils. Financial difficulties may come in the way of the realisation of this ambitious and important suggestion, but following the footsteps of Acharyaji, it will always be possible to find, if need arises, some distinguished teachers to work in the spirit of sacrifice with vigour and courage, for the laudable cause of dissemination of knowledge and the progress of our nation. It will be necessary to limit the entry to these institutions only to those scholars who, as Acharyaji said, are 'prepared to dedicate their lives to the enlargement of the bounds of knowledge'. Dr. C. D. Dashmukh also emphasises this point when he says, 'it is all the more necessary that the talent is discovered at the earliest possible stage and is enabled to develop to

its maximum extent, no matter what the environment and circumstances of the individual may be'.

I have deliberately left out of consideration the case of students who have no desire for knowledge but are crazy after degrees for securing high and lucrative positions. They read only those materials which would help them in passing examinations; hence their general knowledge is extremely poor and so is their cultural and literary background. The universities can be saved from the awkward position of having to award degrees to such students if the purpose of the degree-seekers could be satisfied by some other awards or some equivalent or better financially gainful attractions could be found for them which do not necessitate the possession of a university degree.

ACHARYAJI—AN IDEAL TEACHER OF CHEMISTRY

The Rasarnava, a treatise on alchemy, mentions that a teacher in chemistry should be impartial, free from greed, capable of guiding students, devoid of pride, acquainted with duties, truthful, skilful, virtuous and of good temperament, pure within and without, and aware of the various trends of thoughts in chemistry and details of the laboratory. Accordingly, an ideal teacher should himself be a living example in words, deeds, and character; he should be capable of understanding and visualising the true nature of his disciples and of leading to perfection the potentialities lying dormant in them.

Professor Ray remarkably fulfilled all the above-mentioned requisites. An acknowledged master of chemistry and well-informed about developments in other branches of science, he was one of the leading chemists of his time. Indeed it will not be an exaggeration to say that a teacher like him is one of the rarest human beings.

Prof. Ray taught chemistry at the Presidency College and Science College, Calcutta. His first experience in teaching Chemistry was gained at the University of Edinburgh where, as a Hope Prize Scholar, he assisted Professor Crum Brown in the practical work of students.

During his student days at the Presidency College, Prafulla Chandra was greatly impressed by the method of teaching chemistry followed by Professor Sir Alexander Pedler who, with his remarkable skill, demonstrated experiments during his lectures. In Europe also, the same mode of teaching to undergraduates was followed by even the most reputed and senior teachers. Prof. Ray also adopted and consistently followed the same method in teaching chemistry to junior students. He used to show a good many carefully thought out experiments which made his lectures not only realistic but also easily intelligible. To ensure their success, some of these experiments were repeated several times before these were performed in the class. These instances reveal the great pains Prof. Ray took to see that his students, even the ordinary ones, profited by his teaching and acquired a taste for the study of chemistry.

Professor Ray also earned reputation as a wonderful lecturer. He generally began his lectures with a pleasant introduction and dealt sometimes at length with the historical account of the great discoveries in chemistry, told in the form of stories based on either an anecdote about an investigator or a dramatic or exciting event about some important observations. The touch of human interest, which his fascinating lectures produced, was

invaluable and emphasised 'the real nature of science as a living and growing creation of the human spirit.' The 'brilliance of his exposition' not only made the 'dull atmosphere of the class absorbingly interesting but instilled a thirst for knowledge in young enthusiastic scholars', and thus instead of becoming mere book-worms, they were inspired with the zeal for learning chemistry.

Prafulla Chandra had known that the pupils definitely benefitted if the teachers were generous (large-hearted) and cordial to students, had personal contacts with them, and conversed with them freely. Consequently he put this precept into practice during his teaching career. He was never harsh or cruel or unsympathetic towards his pupils; instead, he had intimate and cordial relations with them. Indeed, his pupils were his friends as well, and 'no incident of his life was hidden from them'. They were his constant companions in work and during evening walks when they could have pleasant talks with him and listen to the leisurely discussions he would have on diverse topics with his friends; these associations were really the most beneficial period of their lives.

The aforesaid qualities of Prof. Ray as a teacher attracted to him the best scholars from all over Bengal and he, by his vast knowledge and practical wisdom, inspired and guided them, made them active and practical, moulded their character, and equipped them with knowledge to enable to rise to eminence; indeed, he dedicated himself to them.

Even with large amounts of money spent these days on education, we have failed to achieve what Acharyaji could do with inadequate funds, poor facilities, and determined discouragement under an alien Government. There is a universal complaint that our students do not achieve the expected high proficiency in learning and there is perennial criticism about falling standards. Usually, the real cause of failure is the poor calibre and the disinterested attitude of the teachers, who have themselves not received their education under the guidance of inspired teachers of the rank of Acharyaji. The practice of lecture-demonstrations has been given up by almost all teachers either on account of their inexperience, inefficiency, non-availability of required pieces of apparatus or want of provision of sufficient time in the teaching hours for this purpose. In any case, this omission is detrimental to science teaching and a serious note of it has to be taken before it unconsciously frustrates the hopes for the development of scientific attitude in young students and defeats the worthy object of propagation of science in our country.

In their lectures also, the present science teachers seldom attempt to familiarise students with the applications of fundamental principles to practical and significant aspects of life as was done by Acharyaji. They begin their lectures not with the narration of a humorous event related to the subject, but with hard and difficultly understandable concepts on the plea of completing the prescribed courses, which are in no case heavy, in a limited time. There is no variety about them; usually these are a system of formulas, which are repeated year after year and are merely good or bad substitutes for books, and hence these lose their value, fail to attract the attention of pupils, and to inspire them or create in them an interest in the subject. If Acharyaji's method of teaching is followed and the lectures are properly thought out and well planned, the standard of science education will positively rise at all levels. According to Acharyaji, 'the teacher is the pivot of all educational effort' and hence it is necessary for him to have 'a forward-looking attitude on the aims of education'. The lack of this outlook, observed in a significant section of teachers of to-day, should be made up by every possible means.

Now-a-days the teachers have little personal contact with their pupils. Through his example, Acharyaji has convincingly shown the necessity of these relations which provide opportunities to teachers to correct the shortcomings of their pupils in right time and enable them to earn the benefit of the experience gained by them.

At present teachers are too much engrossed with their economic worries which naturally affect their capacity to impart their best to the pupils. This genuine difficulty should be remedied at once as it is leading to the deterioration of the education of future generations of our country. Teachers should also realise that they are respected and judged by the labours they devote for the welfare and the proper mental, moral, and spiritual development of the pupils committed to their charge. Acharyaji's success was primarily due to the great sacrifices for the cause of the education of his pupils.

The suggestions made in this and previous sections point to the need for emphasis in the present set-up on a standard 'for the student, the teacher, and the institution'.

ACHARYAJI—AN EMINENT INVESTIGATOR

By nature, man is an inquisitive creature. He has always been curious to know the 'how and why' of things happening in and around him. The search for answers to his questions by probing into the secrets of Nature and unfolding the ways of her working marks the origin of our science. Thus, science is without a beginning, as it has been going on from time immemorial, and without an end, as it would move forward perpetually instead of coming to a dead stop. The advancement of science therefore marks the ascent of man towards progress and his significant conquests over Nature. Therefore, 'To know his science, to know the lives of the men who have made his science, is to know Man and to understand the most inspiring side of human nature'.

Prafulla Chandra Ray was one of these gifted and inspired scientific investigators. The beginning in the pursuit of chemistry made at Calcutta developed greatly at Edinburgh; hence, contrary to the present-day practice, he was not satisfied merely with the completion of his work for the degree, but continued it for one more year even under difficult circumstances.

In India, Prof. Ray started his research work at the old chemical laboratories of the Presidency College, which were ill-equipped and ill-provided with essential requirements, and carried out an investigation to completion. His research activities gained considerable momentum when a new building was constructed to house the chemical laboratory of the college and later when he was appointed the Palit Professor of Chemistry at the Science College. It was at the Presidency College that he made the historic discovery of a method of preparation of mercurous nitrite in a stable and crystalline form, studied its chemical behaviour, and elucidated the mechanism of its formation and structure. This discovery and his other researches on nitrites received high appreciation from some of the most distinguished chemists of the time and brought him worldwide fame. Sir William Ramsay spoke about him as 'an eminent Indian chemist whose name is familiar to us for his most interesting researches on nitrites'. Moissan has extensively described his work in his treatise on Inorganic Chemistry. H. E. Armstrong gave him the title of 'Master of Nitrites'.

The work on mercurous nitrite led Prof. Ray to extend his studies to hyponitrites, the nitrites of alkali and alkaline earth metals, ammonium nitrites having alkyl and aryl groups, the double nitrites of mercury and other metals which were later shown by him to be complex compounds, mercuric nitrite which could not be obtained at that time in solid state, and dimercuriammonium compounds on which he also worked at Davy-Faraday Laboratories, London, during his deputation to England by the Bengal Government. His extensive studies on reactions between mercuric nitrite and mercaptans led him to differentiate between what he called true and potential mercaptans.

Prof. Ray also studied the intricate problem of valencies of platinum, gold, and iridium, which had baffled many investigators, and established their varying values. Besides, he showed that the constitution of some of the compounds of these metals prepared by him could be represented on the basis of Werner's theory.

Good many of his earlier researches were conducted singly; subsequent ones were carried out with the collaboration of his research students. The details of these investigations are available in 143 papers published by him in several scientific journals and the articles mentioned in earlier part of my Address. These contributions went a long way in restoring the declined prestige of Indian chemical research, which was zealously pursued in ancient days, and placed India once again on the scientific map of the world. On this achievement he said that 'while a student at Edinburgh, I almost dreamt a dream that, God willing, a time would come when modern India would also be in a position to contribute her quota to the world's stock of knowledge, and it has been my good fortune to see my dream materialise'.

Prof. Ray was dexterous with his hands and his experimental skill was undoubtedly superb. He also kept himself fully conversant with the latest advancements in science, which enabled him to employ several chemical and physico-chemical methods for the determination of the constitutions and structures of the compounds prepared by him during his investigations.

The discovery of mercurous nitrite by Prof. Ray may be considered by some as a stroke of good fortune, but it has to be accepted that his chemical achievements were due to his ability to observe minutely what happens, to understand what is observed, and to use the information to discover new facts. Truly speaking, these achievements are not a correct measure of his vigour and intellect; they would have certainly been much more, had he not been working under difficult circumstances in unfavourable and hostile environments. His devotion to chemistry was remarkable and so were the labours he put in its pursuit by working from morning till evening all the days of the year, with only a short break during summer.

Thus, Acharyaji's research work, spread over long years, conveys to us that 'glorious edifices, excellent equipment, and abundant staff are of no avail if the true spirit of research is not there', and that 'research atmosphere develops from selfless devotion of both the teachers and the pupils who must work together for the glory of science'. This message of Acharyaji should be remembered by all researchers in India for all time to come.

It is regrettable that not an inconsiderable number of research scholars in our country take up research not with the object of discovering some truth and adding to the fund of knowledge, but with the lure of securing a doctorate degree awarded every year to not a

few. These scholars usually have little comprehension of the scope of the subject of their study; they have neither followed its development since its origin nor are they fully acquainted with its latest position, and have no knowledge on its bearing on and relation with other subjects. The need for the degree arises because of the requirement of attractive appointments to high salaried posts of teachers in universities and of scientific personnel in departments of Government and specialised institutions.

Unless employed in departments of scientific research, many of these doctors not only discontinue their research work after completing it for the degree but also cease to keep themselves in touch with the latest developments. If they get attached to a laboratory, they would generally complain about lack of suitable equipment or point out many shortcomings which come in the way of their work. Further, they would try to avoid working with their own hands and would not devote the time and attention necessary for conducting an investigation. This is unlike a true devotee who would never think of leaving his laboratory even for a moment, unless called away by some very urgent work.

The aforesaid remarks pertain solely to those research scholars who are primarily interested in the degree and not in research. It is imperative that the waste of effort, time, and money for the sake of such scholars should be avoided. One of the ways to achieve this is for the research guides to select scholars for research work on the basis of their interest in and keenness for research and not on their eagerness for obtaining the doctorate degree. This will enable us to screen out real research talents in this country.

It is highly gratifying to note that the ideals set by Acharyaaji continue to be followed by honest and zealous research workers. It is on account of these genuine lovers of science and devoted seekers after truth that scientific research in India has made considerable progress which is being duly recognised and appreciated in the world of science. The pace set by Acharyaaji has been maintained by his pupils and many other workers who have entered the domain of research.

ACHARYAJI—THE FOUNDER OF THE SCHOOL OF CHEMISTRY IN INDIA

It has always been and will probably ever be the tradition of people, who attain the summit of knowledge in any sphere of life's activity, to impart their knowledge to others deserving to receive it. This had led to the establishment of diverse schools of thought. In some of them the dictated practices have to be strictly followed by disciples, who desire to gain all the knowledge possessed by the leader, but restrictions on freedom of thought in such schools often lead to sectarianism and stagnation. *Ashrams* in ancient India were schools of another type; these aimed at developing the talents of disciples, and hence their practices were not rigid but differed in individual cases. Schools of research imply advancement of knowledge; hence the master-minds, who lead these schools, always desire to see their pupils widening the horizons of knowledge and establishing their own schools, which give rise to a chain of schools with the master at the top.

Prof. Ray was the first Indian chemist to establish the first school of chemistry in modern India. Students, who had known of his reputation as a master of chemical knowledge, went to him in numbers for conducting research under his guidance, but he selected only those who could satisfy him as regards their experimental skill in carrying out known

processes under specified instructions and their ability to refer to literature. Thus, he collected a team of keen research scholars, who constituted Dr. Ray's school of chemistry. This school contributed its mite to the world's store of scientific knowledge and established its claim to a high and recognised place in the world of science. Prof. Sylvain Levy looked upon it as 'the nursery of young chemists of India'. Prof. Ray sometimes used to feel that Indian students were generally not as active as their European counterparts and hence he continually instilled in the scholars of his school a passion for research. All scholars worked as a team. The seniors gave the benefit of their experience to the juniors and thus automatically received the training in functioning as independent research guides.

When these scholars left the school to occupy responsible positions as Professors of Chemistry in universities or heads of research departments, they either opened out new lines of research or contributed largely to the advancement of subjects which had been newly developing in those days. Following the foot-steps of their master and his traditions, they worked sincerely, keenly, and enthusiastically day and night and by their brilliant contributions rose to fame in the chemical world and earned their rewards. Most of them established their own school. This led to the growth of a chain of schools of chemistry in India with Acharya Ray as its fountain head. Acharyaji used to pay occasional visits to these schools in later years of his life.

Prof. Ray treated these scholars as his own sons and functioned as their Rishi-Guru. He always took genuine pride in their achievements and the consequent recognition gained by them. He often used to say that his pupils have won greater renown than himself. On one occasion he said 'my pupils are the treasures I have piled up in my career'.

As a rule, scientists are always keen on letting others know what they have discovered and what they have thought. This attitude makes science an essentially collective enterprise and communication, its life-blood, the communicating media being the scientific journals. Hence when a plan was formulated for the establishment of a chemical society in India, Prof. Ray gave all encouragement, inspiration, and support to it and agreed to be its Founder President, mainly because that would 'lead to the rapid and adequate publication of new knowledge and tend ultimately to the real advance of chemistry' in the country. The publication of the *Journal by the Society* was considered by the *Journal 'Nature'* as 'a welcome development in Indian chemistry'. Since its foundation, the Society has done a good deal for the furtherance and propagation of knowledge and dissemination of the research activities of Indian chemists.

The founding of the school of chemistry by Acharyaji has been the basis of the progress of chemical research in India. He really placed Indian chemistry on the path which is leading it to the great heights attained by chemists in other parts of the world. In fact, he said 'our students will one day by the brilliance, volume, and intensity of their work illumine the whole of our beloved motherland'. We have to-day many flourishing schools of chemistry in several parts of India where, according to the practice of Acharyaji, the leaders and the pupils of the schools are actively engaged in research day and night without enjoying many holidays. However, some of these scholars do not reach the high standard, attained and maintained by good many pupils of Acharyaji. This is probably due to adverse economic circumstances of the pupils or want of courage on their part for the needed sacrifice or, in a few cases, to the failure of the leaders to inspire them with the zeal for research to the desired extent. Much attention need not be paid to this situation

as it would disappear with the growth of the spirit of selfless service and painstaking labours of the scholars.

There is a growing tendency amongst the leaders of schools to give too much to publicity not only to their work but also to their movements, probably to glorify themselves. This is contrary to the message of Acharyaji who never gave any publicity to his own self. It will definitely do a lot of good if they 'follow their work quietly and in silence and aim at achieving something really worthwhile'.

ACHARYAJI—THE FOUNDER OF INDUSTRIES IN INDIA

Reading of innumerable scientific discoveries makes one feel that man has made science. But if we look to the changes, which our mode of living has undergone from the stage of cave-man to the modern press-button system providing innumerable facilities and comforts, we will be led to the belief that science has made man. The change has been brought about by the exploitation of scientific discoveries by industrially minded businessmen for the manufacture of a variety of articles which were inconceivable at one time. The applications of science to industry, which form the basis of modern technology and civilisation, have also widened the scope of scientific researches. These are no longer limited to pure or fundamental science but are also directed towards elucidation of technical problems in industry to enhance the efficiency in industrial operations. This needs close association of men of science, either as employees or consultants, with industrial organisations.

During his stay in England, Prof. Ray had visited several chemical works and saw the harnessing of science by advanced nations for their economic progress, to increase their national wealth, and to mitigate human suffering. When Acharyaji saw the miserable conditions of the people of Bengal, he felt that the only means to ameliorate their sufferings and to make them prosperous was to employ scientific knowledge for the creation of industries, and he proclaimed these views publicly. Although he himself had no industrial experience, yet in view of the expectation of the nation from a scientist, Acharyaji utilised his scientific knowledge for the establishment of industries in India. He gave free, valuable advice to all persons who showed an inclination to start an industry in Bengal. He expected that science graduates of Bengal would themselves be fired with a zeal for starting several small-scale chemical industries and use their knowledge of chemistry to advance them and make them successful, but was sorely disappointed to find that this did not materialise. He once asked one of his pupils to give up the chair of Chemistry in a University and take up the Director's post in the Production Department of the Government of India, mainly with a view to hastening the growth of industries in the country.

To enable the people of Bengal to earn decent livelihood, Acharyaji inspired them to work in any position in a manufacturing concern and to take to business and trade, as these vocations were not derogatory to their prestige, but good dignified means of earning. This advice was sincerely followed by many people.

Several manufacturing concerns made commendable progress under Prof. Ray's guidance. Of these, his greatest achievement was the setting up of the Bengal Chemical and Pharmaceutical Works; this was in fact personally started by him on a small scale in the out-houses of his residence with his own finances. The beginning was made with the

preparation of simple chemicals and drugs, which could be prepared easily without requiring much time and large capital. For this purpose, after finishing his teaching and research work at the College, Prof. Ray used to work single-handed for long hours to see that all orders were executed. These early "Works" were later converted into a Public Limited Company, which at present has a capital of a few crores and has several thousand workers. The manufacturing processes are now conducted by the latest scientific methods in up-to-date factories situated at Maniktala and Pannihati where besides chemicals and pharmaceuticals, scientific apparatus and biological preparations are also made.

The pioneering work of Acharyaji in arousing an awakening for industrialisation in our country is indeed very noble and praiseworthy. Had he been living to-day, he would have seen that independent India followed his message faithfully, but contrary to his desire most of the industries do not employ outstanding scientists and do not have research departments to help them to enhance their efficiency.

Furthermore, there is very little contact between industry and teaching institutions. Acharyaji had shown that industries stand to profit by their association with scientists engaged in research in colleges and universities. If this experience is utilised by present industries, their employment of scientists as paid consultants will help them to improve their products and to stabilise their finance. Of course, as Acharyaji did, these scientists will have to work beyond the normal hours assigned for their teaching and research. Discrimination on the part of industrialists towards putting into practice the suggested co-operation on the pretext of scanty income should be carefully studied and suitably overcome.

ACHARYAJI—A BRILLIANT WRITER

An outstanding literary work springs from the depth and fulness of the intellect and robustness of thought and feeling of an enlightened author. The purpose of an author is to communicate ultimately to the understanding or reason of the vast majority of his readers. The standard of his writing is determined by the purity and the exactness of his style and command over the language which he uses for expression of his ideas. Therefore, a writer has to be a great thinker and should possess a wealth of advanced knowledge, new angle of vision or new ideas on a subject, originality and creativeness; his main objective should be the service of mankind.

Acharyaji had a master's command over English and Bengali, originality in thought and expression, and an intense desire to educate people to enable them to think for themselves for their own good and for the good of the country; hence it is not surprising to find that he took to writing at an early age. His first work, which attracted public attention and received great appreciation, was the essay entitled 'The condition of India', written for a prize announced by the University of Edinburgh; it was later printed under the title 'India before and after the Mutiny'. The essay was a critical assessment of the real situation prevailing in India at that time, and contained information about India not found elsewhere. It bore marks of rare ability and revealed the capacity of Acharyaji for wide, deep, and thorough study of a subject. This publication also showed that Acharyaji had the necessary aptitude for the presentation of a subject in modern language with the perfection comparable with that of the best writers of his time.

Prof. Ray had known about Indian alchemy and the chemical knowledge, which ancient Hindus possessed and used for the preparation of Ayurvedic medicines, but no systematic account of it was available in any book. His contact with Berthelot led him to write the History of Hindu Chemistry in the two volumes, which brought to light the scientific work of the ancient Hindus and Hindu civilisation; Prof. Ray thus revived the literature which had declined, consequent on the decline of the nation. This was the second epoch-making publication from Prof. Ray and it was 'a perfectly original contribution to the history of chemical science'. This book shows his 'masterly grasp of facts, wonderful perseverance, admirable linguistic acquirements, rare power of investigation, and a deep knowledge of Sanskrit literature'

A master in the art of writing, Dr. Ray wrote many thought-provoking and informative articles on scientific subjects and topics of social interest. The addresses which he delivered to several universities, scientific bodies, and cultural, social, and political organisations are also compositions of the highest order and reveal the profundity of his thoughts and the elegance of his style.

Being a devoted student of Bengali, he made sustained effort to elevate the language to a high pedestal of honour. Following the example of the patriotic Russian chemist, Mendeloeff, he wanted that all scientific work done in Bengal should be published in Bengali.

The literary works produced by Acharyaji was not intended for financial gains. A judgement on his abilities cannot be based merely on his writings, for, according to the accepted principle, these only partially reveal the author.

In independent India great need is felt for the creation of Indian literature in Indian languages on scientific and other subjects, evidently because if a country has no literature of its own, it does not stand high in the esteem of others. For some reasons, this has not been achieved to the desired extent, inspite of the large funds made available for the purpose. It cannot be due to the shortage of men in the country who are competent to write original books on new subjects or present the published subject matter with a new orientation. In England and America, a number of new books are published every year on various subjects, and sometimes several books are brought out on the same subject by different publishers with a new treatment of the subject. The printing and the get-up of these books are excellent and attractive. Our shortcoming may therefore be due to our publishing houses, which are not yet properly and fully developed as their counterparts in other countries, and, probably, also due to the reluctance of the authors who fail to get adequate return for their labours. These problems need fullest attention and early solution. Attempts should also be made by our senior authors to introduce the latest methods of compilation of chapters written by different experts for the publication of comprehensive books on various subjects in Indian languages.

There is an urgent need for the popularisation of science amongst our people. This purpose can be fulfilled only when articles are written and talks are delivered in easily intelligible style in non-technical language by responsible persons fired with the zeal for a good public cause. This important and urgent work, begun by Acharyaji, should not be left unattended and should in no case be neglected.

ACHARYAJI—A REAL PHILANTHROPIST

Vedas have ordained that one should give away all or part of the wealth acquired and accumulated through honest labour to deserving persons without the feeling of elation. Vyasa, the author of *Mahabharat*, also directed Arjuna 'to protect the poor and not to give to those who are already rich'. According to *Bhagavat Gita*, such gifts, given in cash or kind, are the best gifts. Charities given to get rid of persons are no gifts; they are definite social evils.

Acharyaji had known, probably through the study of Hindu scriptures, that gifts can be given only by those who are prepared to renounce the luxuries and comforts of the world, and sometimes even necessities of life as well. Hence he led a life of utmost simplicity, never yielded to bad habits, lived in celibacy and saintly purity, and denied all pleasures and enjoyments of life, and all prospects of worldly advancements. He had reduced his personal needs to the barest minimum for he believed that indiscriminate multiplication of wants is not conducive to leading a happy and contented life. Therefore the savings from his honest earnings sometimes used to mount up to several thousands of rupees. A parallel to Acharyaji is found in the life of one of the world's greatest scientists, Henry Cavendish, who was very rich but lived a simple life.

Acharyaji was opposed to extravagance. This attitude had its effect not only on his personal life but also in the laboratory where little bits of unused papers were used to write notes, and the burners were never left burning and the water taps running.

Acharyaji's savings were used to help the poor and the needy students, and for the development of industries and the spread of education. His well-known donations are: a substantial amount to the Calcutta University for the annual award of a medal in the name of the Indian genius, Nagarjuna, to the best worker in chemistry; the honoraria received for delivering Addresses or Lectures to the institutions concerned for the award of a prize to the best worker in chemistry; his whole salary for the work done as Professor of Chemistry for five years after the age of retirement to the chemistry department of the Palit laboratory for its development; his entire shares in Bengal Chemical and Pharmaceutical Works, amounting to more than a lakh of rupees, for the organisation and propagation of *Khaddar* industry in Bengal.

The above account does inspire one to try to lead a life according to the ways shown by Acharyaji. I know of some teacher-scientists who tried to live a simple life and donated large sums out of their earnings for the promotion of scientific education and scientific research in our country, and benevolently helped the deserving poor students, but it will be difficult for every teacher and scientist in India to live like Acharyaji on account of the present economic hardship. In spite of this handicap, the ill-paid teachers and scientists are generally more generous than the well-to-do persons. Moreover, the charities given by these persons are seldom without motive and hence lose their significance as good gifts. The habit of giving away to true charities is essentially good and should be developed by every individual as it does away with dishonest mode of earning, encourages hard and sincere labour, removes social evils, greed and jealousy, which are the primary causes of most crimes, and helps the poor and the needy. Evidently, this was the source of the bliss which Acharyaji enjoyed throughout his life.

ACHARYAJI—AN ADMIRABLE SOCIAL WORKER

Lord Buddha, who showed to the people the eight-step path to overcome their sufferings in the widest sense, can be considered to be the greatest social worker. Emperor Asoka was also a social worker as he gave the highest priority to the welfare of the people.

Sometimes sufferings come to people on account of natural calamities which cause heavy devastation and considerable loss of life and are relieved only by the active material help from the rescuers. In ancient and mediæval India the relief work was done by kings who had compassion for their people and who possessed the spirit of service to humanity in the name of God. Subsequently, this responsibility was shifted to the alien Government which acted on the reports of its deputies and was little concerned with the actual hardships experienced by the people. Support from the public was then the only remedy; this gave rise to social workers' organisations which have now spread throughout the country.

Temperamentally Acharyaji could not bear the sight of people in misery and hence, when any sufferings came to them, he was the first to come forward to help them. Two significant events in this connection are noteworthy: (1) the famine in the villages of Khulna which caused several deaths due to starvation, and (2) the flood in a district of North Bengal which washed away human beings, cattle, standing crops, and the houses in the area. On Acharyaji's solicitations people spontaneously volunteered their services and donated large sums for the relief of sufferers, in spite of the apathy of the Government. The great humanitarian work done by Acharyaji was appreciated in all quarters in India and abroad. The secret of Acharyaji's success was the implicit faith of people in his honesty and sincerity.

These qualities of Acharyaji and his love for people are worthy of emulation, not only by teachers and scientists but by other people as well. The social workers' institutions should note that for their successful working they should have a leader like Acharyaji in whom people have full confidence; the workers of the team should be well-disciplined and obedient, physically and mentally strong to work hard, intelligently and conscientiously, and should not be lovers of ease; the plan of their undertakings should be well thought out and organised on reasonably sound basis.

ACHARYAJI—AN ENTHUSIASTIC SOCIAL REFORMER

Man is a social being; hence there is an urge in him to live in the company of others and establish society. In an ideal society, all fellow human beings have a place and are treated without any distinction. Every society has certain customs and cultural background which determine the intellectual, moral, and material life of its members and they change as civilisation advances. However, with the imposition of a civilisation, contrary to the heritage of the society, various adjustments or modifications in these customs have to be necessarily made for the protection of its traditions and to suit the new situations; these changes are definitely not in the interest of the progress of the society and introduce evils.

On account of the subjugation of India by foreign nations with diverse civilisations, several abuses and manifold superstitions crept in our society which then, as now, affected the very vitals of the nation. The reformers therefore undertake an up-hill task for the

redemption of the people from the undesirable practices, and many fail, but they should not feel disappointed as the eradication of social evils is a slow process and demands infinite patience and persistent selfless efforts of reformers. A socially useful achievement has therefore far-reaching consequences and means a real service to the nation.

Inspiration for social reforms came to Acharyaji from his father who, for his advanced outlook, was himself a reformist of the society, and the Brahma Samaj and its ardent followers. Acharyaji used to feel very disturbed to see some basic weakness in Indian social structure. Of these, the plight of a section of our fellowmen, the untouchables, hurt him most; they were then treated with cruelty and contempt as their mere glance at the food of the twice-born was supposed to cause pollution. Realising that the creation of this community was due to the caste system, which was then as now reigning supreme in Hindu society, he condemned this fraudulent and demoralising institution, which caused hatred amongst the people of the same society, in the strongest terms on all occasions, and worked hard to eliminate it by encouraging inter-communal and even international marriages. He was convinced that so long as the evil of untouchability was not removed, the problem of nation-building and development of national character would remain unsolved.

Acharyaji strongly resented the denial of education to Indian women and the compulsion on their living in purdah. Both he and his father, who had already started a girl's school in early days of social awakening, agitated for the spread of female education from economic, political, social, and cultural considerations and for the removal of purdah which enslaved our women, deprived them of social status and thus paralysed the society. He also vehemently opposed the custom of early marriages as they led to an increase in wants, added to miseries, and thus retarded the process of national reconstruction. He used to advise his pupils to non-co-operate with this practice and save themselves from ruining their future career and spoiling their family life.

It will indeed be interesting to know how Acharyaji could find time, energy, and the required concentration of mind to conduct the difficult work of the reformation of the society which baffles even whole-time workers. It was the firmness of his determination and the strength of his will which led him to work whole-heartedly for any cause he espoused.

This example of Acharyaji could be followed and practised by science students, though the way is long and weary, and one might dread to tread on it, knowing that the valiants have not always succeeded. The suggestion is based on the consideration of the mental equipment of these students for this purpose; they have a systematic way of thinking, are accurate and honest in their actions, have the necessary industry to push an attempt forward, and a sincere desire to achieve success. If teams are organised of science students, whose number is increasing every day, and each member of the team does his share of work during holidays and vacations, the collected drops will form an ocean. Want of spare time should be no excuse, for like Acharyaji, some leisure will have to be sacrificed for this noble cause. Several social welfare institutions, organised by the public and the Government, are already engaged in this work; the additional association of science students in this venture will be most welcome.

ACHARYAJI—A TRUE PATRIOT

The first concern of a patriot is the good and the welfare of his country. One who loves and respects his country more than his own life is a worthy patriot, because this is one of the loftiest virtues. Hence in all actions the main consideration with a patriot is his country; nothing else matters for him.

Acharyaji was a genuine patriot because every activity of his life was guided by the motive for developing national character of the people and the building of a prosperous, happy, and enlightened Indian nation. Therefore in spite of the Government honouring him on several occasions, he never missed a single opportunity of criticising it for any unjust treatment meted to Indians, or for disregard of their merit and efficiency, or for preventing the development of Indian industries, and the dissemination of scientific knowledge, or for any action taken to disturb the peace, or to undermine the prosperity and welfare of the motherland. He also condemned the repressive policy of the Government towards national movement and the harsh and cruel treatment meted out to persons who spoke against its atrocities.

Although he did not plunge into the political movement directed for the liberation of India from foreign yoke, Acharyaji, like several scientists, who closed their laboratories and laid down their lives for the cause of the freedom of their countries, realised the claims of the country upon him for his joining the freedom fight, and said 'science can wait but swaraj cannot'. His contribution to the scheme of charka and khaddar, formulated as a part of the programme for the attainment of independence, was remarkable. He worked unceasingly and zealously for popularising charka by distributing hundreds of them free of cost, and appealing to people to work on it during their free hours in their homes, thereby improving their own finances and the national wealth and helping the political movement. He further considered that charka and khaddar could help people to develop character, increase patience and devotion, inculcate industriousness, and remove indolence, and thereby train them in self-reliance. He therefore advocated that cloth, like food, should be prepared in every home from home-grown cotton; hence he arranged for the free distribution of cotton seeds all over Bengal. The successes achieved by Acharyaji in these efforts earned for him the name of an 'apostle of khaddar' just as his scientific pursuits brought him the name of 'saint of science'.

Independence has now been won, but the problems of the rebuilding of the country and the desired improvement in the welfare of the people still remain unsolved. Therefore in the present favourable circumstances efforts for their solution are to be made, more intensely and vigorously than before, until every individual in the country is well-fed and well-clad, and imbibes nationalistic spirit to walk shoulder to shoulder with other countries of the world. Success will be achieved quickly and effectively if the work is pursued with the inspiration and zeal of Acharyaji for which there can be no better appreciation than the remarks that 'Gandhiji would have attained swaraj within one year if he had two more workers of the quality of Acharyaji working with him.'

To-day a critical situation prevails in our national life because of Chinese aggression. The inspiration instilled by Acharyaji in the foundation of the Indian Chemical Society has evidently guided its fellows to pledge themselves to the service of the motherland until the crisis is over. This means that the services of capable and talented chemists are at the

disposal of the country and should be profitably utilised either by assigning them some problems for investigation in their laboratories or seeking their collaboration in the perfection of processes for large-scale production.

CONCLUSION

I have tried my best to do justice to several outstanding facets of Acharyaji's life and to stress their significance with a desire that they would make an appeal to our young chemists and interest the readers in the marvellous selfless work done by him for the scientific, economic, and social progress of our country. It should not lead people to think that in so doing I have exhibited the common tendency to glorify him.

Born as he was in a well-to-do family, Acharyaji could have enjoyed all comforts of life, but he chose to lead a life of great hardship for the emancipation of our country which on account of political bondage and economic servitude was considered at one time to be a dead nation. Being a friend of the poor and the down-trodden, he strived his utmost to do good to them, relieve them from their sufferings, and to secure for them a place of honour in the society.

Acharyaji's way of living was simple, sincere, honest, pure, and devotional and hence he believed, as Shri Rajaji said recently, that 'There is hope if the young men and women of our country vow to live simply, and to be honest under any circumstances and in any employment. Education is of no use if this dedicated spirit does not crown the acquisition of useful knowledge.' Acharyaji also exemplified, by his deeds and actions, Ruskin's ideal that 'work makes life worthwhile, hence a really good life is a life of labour.'

'An institution is the lengthened shadow of one man' says Emerson, and 'unless he is himself great, he cannot produce a good class of pupils'; this is entirely true in the case of Acharyaji. Emerson also says 'A man-Christ was born and we have Christianity. Fox was born and we have Quakerism. John Wesley was born and we have Methodists'. In the same strain I may say that a P. C. Ray was born and we have Indian School of Chemistry.

Acharyaji is no longer with us, but great men like him never die; they live in the hearts of men. He will ever be the most respected Indian Chemist and Humanitarian. His sterling qualities of head and heart, his profound ability, rare and versatile genius, insight and scintillating wisdom, greatness and ennobling possessions, and wonderful capacity for work will ever be remembered by posterity with reverence and esteem. Acharyaji chose the right with invincible resolution, he resisted the severest temptations within and without, he bore the heaviest burdens cheerfully, and above all his reliance on truth, virtue, and God ever remained unfaltering. The future generation will really wonder whether a man like him ever lived on this earth.

I conclude this address with the hope that all scholars, teachers, scientists, industrialists, authors, philanthropists, social workers, social reformers, and the young patriots would derive inspiration from the Message of Acharyaji, act not leisurely but relentlessly with his zeal, devotion and spirit of sacrifice, and reduce their wants to the minimum for meeting the needs of the unfortunate many, to enable India emerge out of its miseries, wants, and evils in which it has been plunged for ages.

JAR HIND